

CHRONIC CEREBRAL ISCHEMIA - A SPECTRUM OF NEUROLOGICAL CLINICS AND PSYCHOEMOTIONAL DISORDERS

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Abstract. *The paper presents the results of a study of 60 patients with various stages of chronic cerebral ischemia who were treated in the neurological department of the Neuromed Service clinic and the Neurology Department of the Central Clinical Hospital of JSC "Uzbekistan Railways". The study included 60 patients with CCI stages 1, 2, 3. All patients were examined in detail for their neurological status and medical history. The duration of patient's complaints, the severity of neurological symptoms, the degree of cognitive impairment, and psychoemotional disorders in CCI were studied.*

Keywords: *chronic cerebral ischemia, neurological status, cognitive and psychoemotional disorders.*

Relevance: According to UN forecasts, in 2025 the number of people over 60 years old will exceed 600 million, which will be more than 15% of the total population of the planet. The increase in the proportion of elderly and senile people in the population, the growth in the number of chronic forms of cerebrovascular pathology, especially with pronounced clinical manifestations and cognitive dysfunctions leading to persistent loss of working capacity, determine the medical and social significance of the problem of diagnosis and treatment of chronic cerebral ischemia [1,2].

In most cases, CCI develops against the background of arterial hypertension and atherosclerotic lesions of the cerebral vessels. Risk factors for the development of CCI and vascular dementia are diabetes mellitus, arterial hypertension, a certain genotype (APOE e4), smoking [3,4]. These vascular risk factors have a direct impact on blood vessels and vascular function. In one study of risk factors for vascular dementia (smoking, hypertension, and diabetes), they were closely associated with the subsequent risk of hospitalization for cognitive decline; this was especially true for middle-aged patients. This association was stronger when risk factors were assessed at a young age and again at an older age [5].

Objective of the study: to study clinical, neurological, and psychoemotional disorders in chronic cerebral ischemia.

Materials and methods of the study: To achieve the set scientific goals and objectives, the work presents the results of a study of 60 patients with various stages of chronic cerebral ischemia (CCI) treated in the neurology department of the Neuromed Service clinic. The study included 60 patients with CCI stages 1,2,3. The inclusion criteria for the study were the age of patients from 55 to 75 years, an established diagnosis of CCI stages 1,2,3 corresponding to the criteria of ICD-10; stable course of the disease for at least 12 months before screening. According to the distribution by gender, among 60 examined patients, there was a predominance of men over women (35 (58%) versus 25 (42%)). The clinical symptoms in 19 (32%) patients corresponded to

CCI stage 1, in 21 (68%) patients - CCI stage 2 with mild and moderate cognitive impairment (classification according to DSM5), in 21 (68%) patients - CCI stage 3.

In all patients, the features of the neurological status, as well as the anamnesis, were studied in detail. When studying the anamnesis, we paid attention to the duration of the development of patient complaints, the severity of neurological symptoms and the degree of cognitive impairment in CCI. We paid attention to the comorbid conditions that were observed in patients in the study groups.

Results of the study: Of the complaints of patients in all study groups, the most common were psychoemotional disorders, signs of asthenization in the form of weakness in 20 (95%) patients with stage 2 of CCI, in 17 (89%) with stage 1 of CCI, and decreased performance, which prevailed in patients with stage 3 of CCI - in 19 (95%), rapid fatigue in 17 (85%). 13 (62%) patients with stage 2 of CCI complained of headache, respectively, with stage 1 of CCI - 10 (53%) and 8 (40%) with stage 3 of CCI, dizziness in 16 (80%) patients with stage 3 of CCI, 12 (57%) patients with stage 2 of CCI and 4 (21%) with stage 1 of CCI, sleep disturbances, respectively - 16 (80%); 15 (71%); 10 (53%), tinnitus occurred in 17 (85%); 13 (62%); 7 (37%) patients, respectively, excessive irritability and nervousness in behavior in 14 (70%); 13 (62%); 8 (42%) patients with CCI. It should be noted that of all study groups, complaints prevailed in patients with CCI stages 3 and 2, while with CCI stage 1 they were less pronounced.

It should be noted that patients in the group with stage 1 of CCI, despite complaints of decreased memory, performance, and increased fatigue, were active and independently performed their duties at work. In the group of patients with stage 2 of CCI, activity was also noted, but patients complained of decreased memory and performance, accompanied by a decrease in cognitive skills. Patients with stage 3 of CCI constantly needed care.

Analysis of focal neurological symptoms showed: central paresis of the VII pair of cranial nerves was detected in 3 (16%) with stage 1 of CCI, 5 (24%) patients with stage 2 of CCI, and 12 (60%) patients with stage 3 of CCI; central paresis of the XII pair of cranial nerves occurred in 1 (5%), 2 (10%), and 7 (35%) of those examined in the groups, respectively. Oral automatism reflexes were observed in 8 (38%) patients with stage 2 of CCI, 16 (80%) with stage 3 of CCI, respectively; anisoreflexia was diagnosed in 5 (26%) patients with stage 1 of CCI, 9 (47%) patients with stage 2 of CCI, and 12 (60%) patients with stage 3 of CCI; ataxia – in 4 (21%), 11 (52%), 18 (90%) patients, respectively; unsteadiness in the Romberg position in 4 (21%), 12 (57%), 16 (80%) patients, respectively, intention when performing the finger-nose test in 4 (21%), 10 (58%), 15 (75%) patients with CCI, respectively; intention when performing heel-knee in 4 (21%), 12 (57%), 16 (80%) patients, respectively, dysarthria in 1 (5%), 6 (29%), 7 (35%) patients, respectively; cognitive impairment in 7 (37%), 16 (76%), 18 (90%) patients.

We present the results of experimental psychological studies - analysis of the cognitive sphere of patients with CCI. Neuropsychological examination began with the Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE). In the control group, the mental state indicators on the MMSE scale revealed a score of 29.8 ± 0.1 , which was close to the norm (30 points). In all patients with CCI stage 1, the score was 28.6 ± 0.2 , which corresponded to proximity to the norm and mild cognitive impairment; in patients with stage 2 CCI - 26.5 ± 0.1 , which corresponds to moderate cognitive impairment; in patients with stage 3 CCI - 24.3 ± 0.1 ($P < 0.001$), which corresponded to pre-dementia cognitive impairment.

When conducting the Frontal Assessment Battery (FAB, B. Dubois et al., 1999), a test designed to identify dementia with predominant damage to the frontal lobes or subcortical formations of the brain, the control group showed 18.01 ± 0.1 points, which corresponds to normal frontal function. Whereas in patients with stage 1 of CCI - 24.3 ± 0.1 ($P < 0.001$), which corresponded to pre-dementia cognitive impairment. In patients with stage 1 of CCI 17.4 ± 0.02 points were noted, in patients with stage 2 of CCI - 15.6 ± 0.30 , in patients with stage 3 of CCI - 13.7 ± 0.33 , which confirms the presence of moderate frontal dysfunction, most pronounced in the group of patients with stage 3 of CCI.

The Beck Anxiety Scale (BAS) was used to assess the severity of psycho-emotional disorders. At the time of inclusion in the study, the most common complaints of patients were psychoemotional disorders, signs of asthenia in the form of weakness, rapid fatigue, patients complained of headaches, sleep disturbances at night, excessive irritability and nervousness in behavior, isolation, more pronounced in the group of patients with stage 2 and 3 of CCI. The study of the psycho-emotional state using the Beck Anxiety Scale showed that the average score of anxiety disorders in the group of patients with stage 1 of CCI was 9.1 ± 1.6 , which corresponds to minor anxiety, while in patients with stage 2 of CCI the average score on the Beck scale was 14.1 ± 0.33 , which corresponds to mild depression, in patients with stage 3 of CCI pre-dementia cognitive impairment and moderate depression were noted, amounting to 21.1 ± 0.2 points on the Beck Depression Scale. To determine the severity of dyslipidemia and determine the biochemical parameters of chronic cerebrovascular disease in the subjects, a comprehensive biochemical blood test was performed using standard methods. It was found that stage 1 of CCI is characterized by moderate dyslipidemia.

Moreover, cholesterol levels were higher in the group with stage 2 of CCI (5.44 ± 0.70) and stage 3 of CCI (5.98 ± 0.43) than in stage 1 of CCI (4.82 ± 0.67). Triglycerides in stage 1 of CCI were 1.89 ± 0.22 , stage 2 of CCI - 2.08 ± 0.21 mmol/l and stage 3 of CCI - 2.36 ± 0.19 mmol, and low-density lipoproteins increased with the stage (2.78 ± 0.88 ; 3.03 ± 0.82 ; 3.25 ± 0.35), respectively, high-density lipoproteins decreased, according to the stages (1.61 ± 0.3 ; 1.40 ± 0.24 ; 1.26 ± 0.2).

Conclusions: Thus, the clinical and neurological examination showed that subjective complaints of a cerebral nature are reliably frequent and are accompanied by asthenia of the nervous system. As for objective symptoms, patients in the group with CCI stage 1 had diffuse focal symptoms, in contrast to the group with CCI stages 2 and 3, where pronounced organic symptoms were noted, with a progradient course, especially in patients with CCI stage 3. Our analysis of the severity of cognitive impairment according to the MMSE and FAB tests showed that patients in the study group with CCI stage 1 had mild ones, with CCI stage 2 there was a cognitive deficit corresponding to moderate cognitive disorders, and patients with CCI stage 3 had pre-dementia cognitive impairment. In chronic cerebral ischemia, all lipid spectrum parameters were outside the normal range, least pronounced in stage 1 of CCI and most pronounced in stage 2 and 3 of CCI.

REFERENCES

1. Antipenko E.A., Deryugina A.V., A.V. Gustov Systemic stress-limiting effect of mexidol in chronic cerebral ischemia // S.S. Korsakov Journal of Neurology and Psychiatry, No. 4, 2016, pp. 28-31

2. Voronina T.A. Pioneer of antioxidant neuroprotection. 20 years in clinical practice // Russian Medical Journal. Neurology, No. 1, 2016.
3. Zakharov V.V. et al. Chronic cerebral circulatory failure: description of a clinical case// Therapeutic archive, No. 4, 2016, pp. 93-98
4. Rummyantseva S.A., et al. Problems and prospects of correction of intermediate metabolism in patients with vascular comorbidity// Neuronews magazine No. 1-2 2014.
5. Chukanova E.I., Chukanova A.S. Efficacy and safety of the drug Mexidol FORTE 250 in the context of sequential therapy in patients with chronic cerebral ischemia// Journal of Neurology and Psychiatry named after S.S. Korsakov 2019, v. 119, No. 9, pp. 39-45